

A Quiet Fight

Dr. James Russo A. Taga
Instructor I/Department Head
Bukidnon State University

I wear a smile though storms are in my mind,
And teach with hands that shake, yet still stay kind.
Before my class, I stand and do my part,
While silent battles thunder through my heart.

I write of hope upon the board each day,
Though some of mine have slowly slipped away.
I guide young souls to rise, to dream, to see,
While searching for that same bright light in me.

There are long nights when sorrow takes its place,
And leaves its shadows drawn across my face.
Yet when the morning calls me back once more,
I choose to stand and walk through that school door.

For I am more than all the pain I hide,
More than the tears I keep so deep inside.
A wounded soul, yet still I choose to fight,
A teacher living through a quiet fight.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20093831

*Copyright & Published in the Philippines ©2026
by Pinagpala Publishing Services*